

Advanced Perception Systems for Intelligent Agricultural Vehicles

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Abstract—This paper describes latest research by the authors in the development of advanced perception systems and methods for intelligent agricultural vehicles. Innovative results in the context of terrain estimation and in-field phenotyping, based on multi-sensor devices integrated on-board mobile robotic platforms, are presented. Aim of this research is to facilitate operations on a narrow scale that may be useful to increase precision during farming operations, as well as to improve the level of driving automation of vehicles by providing fast automated safety responses, traversability assessment and controlled traffic farming in general.

Index Terms—intelligent vehicles, agricultural robotics, terrain estimation, in-field phenotyping

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of intelligent agricultural vehicles, able to operate in the field with limited human supervision, represents one of the major current research challenges in the context of agricultural automation. The use of autonomous or semi-autonomous vehicles equipped with communication and operation synchronization capabilities can significantly contribute to improve the entire production flow, reducing work times and making processes such as plowing, sowing, harvesting and monitoring of growth and status of cultivations, more efficient [1].

A specific objective is to increase the level of driving automation of vehicles, as recognized by the Horizon 2020 Multi-Annual Roadmap for Robotics in Europe (MAR). Although autonomous GPS-based driving systems have been in use for several years, these systems do not provide information on the "dynamics" of the environment. The challenge is to develop intelligent vehicles that can operate in populated environments that change over time. To achieve this objective, further research is needed aimed at the development of advanced perception systems and methods that allow the vehicle to reach adequate levels of understanding and knowledge of the surrounding environment. This knowledge is also important in order to guarantee high safety levels of the vehicle itself, as well as of people, animals and things that are within the operating environment [6].

In this scenario, recent and current research by the authors

Fig. 1. The all-terrain vehicle used for field validation.

carried out in the context of international research projects is aimed at studying and developing multi-sensor perception systems for the characterization of soils and crops through mobile robotic platforms.

II. MULTI-SENSOR TERRAIN ESTIMATION

Terrain assessment is a key issue for the development of intelligent agricultural vehicles. On natural soil, wheel-ground interactions play a critical role for vehicle mobility, which can be radically different on plowed soil rather than on compact soil. The ability to estimate the traversed terrain can contribute to increase the safety of agricultural vehicles near slopes, canals, or on highly deformable ground. Soil characterization can also provide information to predict the risk of soil compaction from farm machinery.

In the context of this research, the problem of terrain assessment was addressed by using a multi-sensor approach, in which data from both proprioceptive and exteroceptive sensors, are integrated for terrain characterization. In particular, a method based on supervised learning techniques was developed to recognize different terrain types [5]. The proposed algorithm aims at identifying the traversed terrain among a predefined number of classes based on proprioceptive characteristics (slippage, vibrations, motion resistance) and exteroceptive features (geometric and color features extracted

Fig. 2. Multi-sensor information acquired by robot on-board sensors during a test on dirt road and gravel. From top to bottom: motion resistance, RMS of vertical acceleration, slip and top view of the 3D stereo map of the traversed terrain. At time T_1 the transition from dirt road to gravel is clearly visible in all graphs.

from stereo images). The validation of the methods was carried out using data acquired in the field by a mobile robot equipped with different sensing devices, as shown in Figure 1. As an example, Figure 2 shows the multi-sensor information acquired by the vehicle for a test on dirt road and gravel. Experimental results showed that it is not only possible to classify various kinds of terrain using either sensor modality, but that these modalities are complementary to each other and can be combined to reach higher classification accuracy.

Another part of the research was concerned with the development of multi-sensor terrain mapping methods [4]. Specifically, three-dimensional visual sensors generate 3D point clouds that provide geometric and visual information, whereas hyperspectral and thermal sensors provide signatures to identify the nature of the observed surfaces. In addition, as the vehicle moves across its operating space and senses the supporting plane through its proprioceptive sensors, the environment representation is augmented with the mechanical properties of the terrain. The registration and integration of all information leads to multi-layer terrain maps. Such maps could be successively processed by using supervised or unsupervised classification methods to generate semantic representation of the environment and specifically of the supporting terrain.

III. IN-FIELD PLANT PHENOTYPING

A grapevine phenotyping platform using an agricultural vehicle equipped with a consumer-grade RGB-D sensor was developed. The system is intended to acquire visual and 3D information to reconstruct the canopy of the plants for geometric measurements, such as plant volume and height, and to detect grapevine clusters. Tests were performed in a commercial test field in Switzerland. As an example, Figure 3 shows the result of the application of computational geometry methods and segmentation algorithms to estimate the height of plants of a vineyard row.

A deep learning approach using visual images and pre-trained CNNs was also developed to segment the scene into multiple classes and in particular to detect grapevine clusters, as shown in Figure 4. Field tests showed that, despite the poor quality of

Fig. 3. Canopy height estimates using RGB-D data. The color of each plant reflects the canopy height according to the color bar shown at the bottom of the figure.

Fig. 4. Grape cluster identification. From left to right: original image; ground-truth (from manual labeling); classifier result. Black, green, blue, red and white colors represent, respectively, background, leaves, wood, pole and bunch classes.

the input images, the proposed methods are able to correctly detect fruits, with a maximum accuracy of 91.52%. More details can be found in [2], [3].

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Innovative results in the context of perception systems for intelligent agricultural vehicles have been illustrated. The activities concerned in particular the development of multi-sensor methods for in-field characterization of soils and crops by ground robotic vehicles.

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